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Sparse Reconstruction for High-Resolution Inverse SAR Imaging

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Abstract

Unknown motion significantly impacts the image quality of inverse synthetic aperture radar (ISAR) images. An auto-focus image reconstruction algorithm plays a key role in reconstructing ISAR images using raw data. In this context, sparse signal recovery has gained attention. Compressive sensing (CS) allows high-quality imaging using less data under sparse scene or target assumptions in certain domains. A 2D image reconstruction directly from raw ISAR data was proposed using a certain resolution factors. Within this framework, we converted the imaging problem into a signal reconstruction problem using a sparse basis. The imaging results of the “Yak-42” demonstrate the performance of the CS technique without relying on preprocessing steps, such as range-compression or motion compensation. The results were compared with the 1D CS approach, which exploits the Pattern-Coupled Sparse Bayesian Learning (PC-SBL), and OMP algorithms.

Keywords

Compressive Sensing, Inverse SAR, Sparsity, PC-SBL, OMP

1. Introduction

As radar technology advances, imaging plays a pivotal role in radar functionality [1, 2]. Methods such as range-Doppler imaging, polar reformatting, matched filtering, and sparse reconstruction are used to reconstruct ISAR images [3]. Compressive Sensing (CS)-based ISAR imaging has gained attention owing to its ability to achieve high-quality results with a reduced number of samples in radar applications [4]. This can be achieved by solving the convex l_1 -norm problem.

Recent studies have focused on exploiting 1D sparsity for ISAR autofocusing with rotational motion compensation. However, this leads to the dislocation of adjacent echo pulses in the range dimension owing to range compression [5, 6]. In addition, azimuthal phase compensation is required to align the echoes for turntable imaging. Furthermore, the complex nonlinear motion of the target renders the image reconstruction challenging.

The primary goal is to enhance the quality of ISAR image reconstruction within the CS framework. Various

techniques such as basis pursuit [7], matching pursuit [8], and thresholding-based methods [9] can be employed to obtain CS reconstructions through the resolution of l_1 -minimization problems. The Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) [10] - a Greedy algorithm - has gained substantial traction in the domain of SAR and ISAR imaging due to its efficiency and robustness.

High-resolution imaging plays a vital role in radar technology and remote sensing. This study focuses on enhancing the target imaging using 2D raw data with certain resolution factors (2^{2F}). The proposed technique does not require a pre-processing chain and introduces a direct reconstruction solution that strategically considers both the computational cost and imaging resolution. Various sparsity factors of the measurement matrix and data are considered to achieve this goal. Section 2 presents the CS-ISAR imaging model and coarse measurements generation, and 1D CS-ISAR Imaging methods. Section 3 details the processing results of the complex ISAR data. Finally, Section 4 presents the conclusions of the study.

2. Compressive Sensing for ISAR

The concept of Compressed Sensing theory asserts that when a vector representing a signal of interest, it can be precisely reconstructed using a limited set of linear, non-adaptive measurements, given that the vector displays sparsity on an orthonormal basis or in a certain domain.

2.1. CS Theory

The ISAR image demonstrates the locations and amplitudes of strong echoes. If the sparse echo contains ‘ P ’

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pulses and the fully observed signal contains ‘ M ’ pulses, with each pulse containing ‘ N ’ sampling points, the under-sampled model of the sparse aperture is provided by $P \ll M$. The classic CS measurement model in the form of a linear system is given by [11]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y} &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{n}, \\ \text{where } \mathbf{X} &= \Phi\Psi, \\ \text{so } \mathbf{Y} &= \Phi\Psi\mathbf{S} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{S} represents the original image (vector) to reconstruct, ‘ \mathbf{Y} ’ is the vectorized version of the ISAR measurements, Φ , and Ψ are Fourier transforms in range and azimuth dimensions respectively. The sensing matrix ‘ \mathbf{A} ’ is a 2D square matrix ($\Phi\Psi \otimes \Phi\Psi$). The measurements in Eq. (1) did not undergo motion compensation and range compression.

2.2. Sensing Matrix

In fact, the ISAR problem is considered an ill-posed inverse problem. Therefore, CS ISAR integrates imaging method, and here we incorporate a the sensing model that implies two Fourier transforms in within measurement matrix (\mathbf{X}) that corresponds to function of ISAR imaging model.

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi &= \{\Phi_1, \Phi_2, \dots, \Phi(q), \dots, \Phi_Q\} \\ \Phi_q &= \exp[-j2\pi \cdot f_d(q) \cdot t] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where f_d is discrete Doppler sequence $[1 : Q]^T \Delta f_d$, and $Q = f_r / \Delta f_d$, f_r is the PRF (pulse repetition frequency). So, together Ψ , and Φ provides the dense dictionary [12].

However, for the reconstruction, we utilized three coarseness scales the $\mathbf{X}_{1/F}$, with a certain resolution factor of 2^{2^F} , where $F \in \{0.25, 0.5, 1\}$. A resolution levels scheme embeds the spatial sparsity of \mathbf{S} to screen out regions with dense information [13]. This allows for reducing the memory requirements while increasing the robustness of the reconstruction.

2.3. 1D CS: PC-SBL

For comparisons 1D compressive sensing using the Pattern-Coupled Sparse Bayesian Learning (PC-SBL) method [14] is utilized. This optimally captures patterns and relevance in neighboring coefficients using hyper-parameters for sparsity. The block diagonal measurement matrix ‘ \mathbf{D} ’ with its i^{th} element equal to $(\alpha_i + \beta\alpha_{i+1} + \beta\alpha_{i-1})$, where α_i are estimated hyper-parameters, and β is a parameter indicating the pattern relevance between the neighbouring coefficients.

2.4. 1D CS: OMP

In the OMP greedy algorithm, the sparse signal approximation is updated in each iteration by orthogonally projecting \mathbf{Y} onto the columns of the sparsifying matrix using the current support set. This process minimizes the l_2 norm over the sparse signal with the support set and ensures that entries are not re-selected. Furthermore, the residual at any iteration is always orthogonal to all currently selected entries. However, this method still relies on an efficient dictionary to reconstruct the target with fewer CPIs. Achieving the best results often involves varying certain dictionaries and iterations through a trial-and-error process [15].

3. Main Results

This section presents three cases: case-I comprising raw data and case-II and case-III involving motion compensated data. Fig. 1(a) and 1(b) illustrate the target geometry and the mapping from observation parameters to k -space components, respectively. In Fig. 1(c), the 2D complex ISAR raw data spectrum is presented, while Fig. 1(d) displays the range-compressed or motion-compensated ISAR data of ‘Yak-42’ [16]. The images shown here are the power of the reconstructed images in the dB scale.

Case-I: Fig. 2(a) shows a completely raw 2D measurement data that was set to reconstruct our target image. The coarser ‘ \mathbf{X} ’ matrix was adapted with 25% of the raw data to reconstruct the target, but with low-level scatters with full of noise, as shown in Fig. 2(b). In Fig. 2(c), a coarse version of ‘ \mathbf{X} ’ matrix is utilized with only 50% of the data, resulting in the reconstruction of the target as well as medium-level scatters as noise. In Fig. 2(d), the

Figure 1: (a) 2D ISAR raw data ‘Yak-42’, (b) Range compressed and motion compensated raw data.

Figure 2: Utilizing completely-raw ISAR data from Fig.1(a). Exploit 2D CS-ISAR image reconstruction using dictionary of Doppler sequences. (a) Full Sensing Matrix, (b) with 25% of full data, (c) with 50% of full data, (d) with full data.

Figure 3: Utilizing range compressed ISAR image data from Fig.1(b). Exploit 1D CS-ISAR image reconstruction using PC-SBL method. (a) Small Diagonal Sensing Matrix, (b) with 50% azimuth data, (c) with 37.5% azimuth data, (d) with 25% azimuth data.

image is reconstructed with full SM and reconstruct only high-level scatters and suppress the noise. This can be enhanced by implementing a greedy algorithm.

Case-II: In the PC-SBL method, the parameter β serves as an indicator of the relevance pattern existing between a coefficient and its adjacent coefficients. The experiments detailed in [14] have effectively demonstrated that the degree of sparsity is skillfully controlled through manipulation of the hyper-parameter, particularly when $\beta > 0$. For simplicity, we designate $\beta = 1$. In Fig. 3(a), the PC-SBL algorithm employs a block-diagonal matrix 'D'. Optimal reconstruction performance is attained by utilizing a dataset amounting to 50% of the azimuthal data, as vividly illustrated in Fig. 3(b). Nonetheless, a no-

ticeable degradation becomes evident when the dataset size is reduced to 37% and 25%, leading to the blurring of strong scatterers, as depicted in Fig. 3(c), and 3(d) respectively. Furthermore, observable deviations in the positions of range pulses are apparent.

Case-III: The efficacy of the Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) algorithm, a greedy approach, is evaluated. This algorithm is distinguished by its attributes of low computational and time complexity, making it favorable for the task of image recovery. The performance of the data reconstruction process is examined across various levels of sparsity, namely 62.5%, 50%, 37.5%, and 25% of the azimuth data. The outcomes of these tests are presented in Fig. 4 (a - d).

Figure 4: Utilizing range compressed ISAR data from Fig.1(b). Exploit 1D CS-ISAR image reconstruction using OMP method. (a) with 62.5% of azimuth data, (b) with 50% azimuth data, (c) with 37.5% azimuth data, (d) with 25% azimuth data.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we utilize a sensing matrix with a certain resolution level of 2^{2F} to reconstruct the target directly from 2D ISAR raw data at certain resolutions. In comparison to the 1D CS-ISAR PC-SBL method, our proposed technique demonstrates its applicability by achieving remarkable imaging results without the need for any pre-processing or reliance on any greedy algorithms. This advancement has brought us closer to practical applications. In the future, we will apply coarse-to-fine estimation to reduce the computational burden and reconstruct clutter-free image to obtain super-resolution for CS-ISAR.

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